

Formulation And Evaluation of SMEDDS of Nabumetone

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ABSTRACT

Microemulsion systems for oral delivery of poorly water-soluble active pharmaceutical ingredient, specifically Nabumetone. Microemulsion, self microemulsifying drug delivery system (SMEDDS) and solid SMEDDS were designed and developed to enhance the solubility and bioavailability of Nabumetone. Capmul MCM/Tween 20/PEG 400 and Capmul MCM/Tween 80/PEG 400 system were employed to formulate microemulsion and SMEDDS, respectively. The optimized liquid SMEDDS formulation was converted into a free flowing powder using solid carriers. The study characterized the drugs using FTIR and UV spectroscopy and determined their solubility in various oils, surfactant, co-surfactants. The results demonstrate the potential of microemulsion and SMEDDS to enhance the solubility and bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs.

Keywords: Microemulsion, Nabumetone, Bioavailability, Capmul MCM, PEG 400, FTIR, UV spectroscopy, Tween 20, Self microemulsifying drug delivery system (SMEDDS)

INTRODUCTION

The oral route is commonly used for drug delivery because of its safety [1], comfort [2], minimum effort [3], and greater patient compliance [4]. However, many drugs have difficulty in developing as oral dosage forms because of their low solubility, low permeability [6], poor bioavailability, delayed onset of action, high inter/intra subject variability [5], and lack of dose linearity [6]. Different parameters, such as aqueous solubility, and rate of dissolution, influence the oral bioavailability of drugs. Susceptibility to efflux mechanisms, first-pass metabolism, and systemic metabolism has all been aspects to consider [7].

Combinatorial chemistry and high throughput screening (in vitro approaches) are used to identify the potent molecules in drug discovery process [8]. In the pharmaceutical research, more than 40% of NCEs (new chemical entities) are practically insoluble in water. Hence many of these promising active

compounds are not considered in clinical-stage development [6]. Solubility of the drug is one of the major parameters to achieve the desired drug concentration in systemic circulation to produce therapeutic activity when administered [9]. The drug dissolution and gastro-intestinal permeability are the fundamental properties controlling the rate and extent of drug absorption [8]. Based on these properties, the biopharmaceutical classification system (BCS) classifies the drugs into four categories: Class

I. High solubility-high permeability [2]; Class II. Low solubility-high permeability [3]; Class III. High solubility-low permeability [4]; Class IV. Low solubility low permeability [10]. Since many of the drugs belong to BCS II and IV their solubility and permeability problems are addressed by using conventional and novel techniques [11].

The conventional techniques are salt forms, solid dispersions [16], use of co-solvents [12], hydrotrophy, micronization, change in dielectric constant of

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solvent, amorphous forms [7], chemical modification of drug, use of surfactants, inclusion complex [3], alteration of pH of solvent, use of hydrates or solvates [6], use of soluble prodrugs [8], application of ultrasonic waves [9], functional polymer technology, controlled precipitation technology [12], evaporative precipitation in aqueous solution [18], use of precipitation inhibitors, solvent deposition [4], precipitation [2], selective adsorption on insoluble carriers [9]. However, conventional approaches have many limitations like for example salt formation [12] of drugs is commonly used but always unattainable. Therefore weak acid and weak base synthesis are not practical [13]. Moreover, the formed salts might be converted into their original form and it may cause the assembling of a weak acid and weak base in the gastrointestinal tract [4]. Reducing particle size might not be advisable because some of the processing problems may arise for amorphous powders [15].

Types of SEDDS

Based on the droplet size SEDDS are categorized into two types [1]: A) self-micro emulsifying drug delivery systems (SMEDDS) [34], B) self-nano emulsifying drug delivery systems (SNEDDS) [16]. SEDDS refers to all forms of self-emulsifying systems [2], containing a mixture of oils, surfactants, and co-solvents (or) co-surfactants [25]. When the mixture of SMEDDS come in contact with the aqueous environment in GIT, they form a microemulsion under gentle agitation provided by the digestive motility of the stomach and intestine [34]. At the same time, SNEDDS refers to systems that generate nanoemulsions when dispersed in aqueous media [16]. The differences between SEDDS, SMEDDS and SNEDDS systems are given in table 3.

Advantages

1. Compared to micro emulsions, nanoemulsions (SNEDDS) have a very wide surface area and free energy (SMEDDS).
2. The Drug Administration's self-emulsification method is critical for improving bioavailability.
3. In addition to their ability to protect drugs from hydrolysis and enzyme degradation, the ability of nano emulsion (SNEDDS) to dissolve large quantities of lipophilic drugs makes them suitable for parenteral transport vehicles.

4. It is necessary for SNEDDS to provide ultra-low interfacial voltage and to provide a wide O/W interface field.

Disadvantages

- Production costs are high.
- Challenges regarding the validation of different components.
- Problems with drug compatibility.

Preparation methods for SNEDDS:

Method of preparation for SNEDDS includes active pharmaceutical ingredient, excipient, polymers and emulsifier. Different methods for the preparation of Self Nano-emulsifying drug delivery system but, mainly divided into 2 methods:

- A. High-energy-emulsification.
- B. Low-energy-emulsification

The high-energy-emulsification method includes higher pressurized-homogenization (HPH), Ultra sonication and Micro-fluidization. The low-energy method includes Phase-inversion, Spontaneous emulsification. Using combination of both technique, such as high-energy emulsification and low-energy emulsification, for prepared reverse Self Nano-emulsifying drug delivery system are highly viscous system.

High Energy Emulsification Method:

1. High pressure homogenisation (HPH):

The preparing of Self Nano-emulsifying drug release system want important compel homogenization. This style above all old as higher-pressurized-homogenizer/locate-homogenizer gives Nano-emulsion particularly muffled particle extent (up to 1nm). This scattering in 2 phases (oil-mixture & aqueous-phase) is attained speeding mixed substance through a trivial cove chops at exact excessive load (500-5000 psi), addresses invention in higher disorder and hydraulic-shear develops an awfully charge particles of emulsion.

2. Ultrasonication:

It is the more convenient method lowering drops sized in this method; the energy-range is given through sonotrodes known to be Sonicator-probe. It bottle hold back piezo-electric quartz precious stone that preserves spread out & tighten the comeback of broken exciting volt. End point in Sonicator contacts the liquid medium; its container produces mechanical throb and captives enrolled. Formation of captives shut down vapour cavities in liquid. Thus, ultrasounds

canister straight produces an emulsion. In this mode is above all old for laboratories purpose, everywhere blend drop dimension.

MATERIALS AND EQUIPMENTS

List of Equipments

List of instruments required for the research work

Sr. No.	Equipment	Model & Make of the Equipment/Instrument
1.	Digital weighing balance	Shimadzu electronic analytical balance
2.	FT IR	FTIR–Brucker alpha-E model
3.	UV spectrophotometer	UV-1800 spectrophotometer, Shimadzu
4.	Magnetic Stirrer	MS500, Remi Equipments
5.	Malvern zetasizer	NanoZSLU-227, Malvern Instruments,
6.	Digital pH meter	Systronic, 361-micropHmeter
7.	Brookfield Viscometer DVII	LVDVII+PRO, Brookfield, USA
8.	Bubble Tensiometer	BPA-800P
9.	Transmission electron microscope	TEM-JEM-100SX, JEOL, Tokyo
10.	Dissolution apparatus	Electrolab TDT-80L
11.	Organ Bath	SE1AW Orchid Scientifics India
12.	HPLC with UV-Visible Detector And HPLC packed column-C18	SPD-10A, Shimadzu
13.	Vortex Mixer	Remi Equipments
14.	Monoocular Electron Microscope	Olympus, 220V
15.	Centrifuge	RM12C, Remi Equipments

List of Materials

List of materials required for the research work

Sr. no.	Name	Category	Supplier of material
1.	Nabumetone IP, BP, USP	API	Aadhar Life Sciences Pvt. Ltd
2.	Capmul MCM	Oil	Abitec Corporation, USA
3.	Capmul MCM C8	Oil	Abitec Corporation, USA
4.	Capmul MCM C10	Oil	Abitec Corporation, USA
5.	Captex 200	Oil	Abitec Corporation, USA
6.	Captex 200P	Oil	Abitec Corporation, USA
7.	Captex 355	Oil	Abitec Corporation, USA
8.	Capryol 90	Oil	Gattefosse, France
9.	Castor oil IP	Oil	Suvidhinath Lab
10.	Olive oil IP	Oil	Sous Cuetora
11.	Isopropylmyristate IP	Oil	S.Dfine Chem
12.	Soyabinoil	Oil	S.Dfine Chem
13.	Tween 80 IP	Surfactant	S.Dfine Chem
14.	Tween 20 IP	Surfactant	S.Dfine Chem
15.	Labrasol	Surfactant	Gattefosse, France
16.	Plurol Oleique	Surfactant	Gattefosse, France
17.	Peceol	Co-surfactant	Gattefosse, France
18.	Transcutol P	Co-surfactant	Gattefosse, France

19.	Polyethylene Glycol 400 (PEG 400) IP	Co-surfactant	SuvidhinathLab
20.	Aerosil200IP, USP	Adsorbent	EvonikDeggussa
21.	Avicel PH 102 BP, USP	Adsorbent	SDfinechem.Ltd.

Experimental Work

List of reagents required for the research work.

Sr.No.	Reagents
1.	0.05M Phosphatebuffer pH7.4
2.	0.1M Hydrochloric Acid (HCl)
3.	0.02M NaOH
4.	Methanol
5.	0.02M Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate

Drug Profile [154-167]

1.Nabumetone Chemical structure:

Chemical Structure of Nabumetone

Molecular Weight: 228.29 **BrandNames:**
RelafenCAS number: 42924-53-8

IUPAC Name: 4-(6-methoxynaphthalen-2-yl)butan-2-one

Molecular Formula: C₁₅H₁₆O₂

Synonyms: nabumetone, Relafen, 4-(6-methoxynaphthalen-2-yl)butan-2-one, Arthaxan.

Melting Point: 78-82°C

Medical uses: Nabumetone is used to treat pain and inflammation.

Type: Small Molecule

Excipients Profile:

1. Capmul MCM

Capmul products are mono-, di- and triglyceride oils prepared through the glycerolysis of select fats and

oils. They can be prepared by esterification of glycerin with specific fatty acids. They are lipophilic, insoluble in water and soluble in oils at elevated temperatures. They are used to produce stable emulsions and to modify viscosity.

Generic name: Mono/diglycerides of caprylic acid

Structure of Capmul MCM

Physiochemical:

Physical State: Soft solid or liquid.

Odor: Fatty odor.

Appearance: Soft solid or liquid.

Vapor Pressure: <1 mmHg at 25°C

Vapor Density: >1 (Air=1)

Solubility in Water: Partially soluble.

Stability and Reactivity: stable at room temperature

Hazardous polymerization: no

Polymerization: product will not undergo polymerization.

Incompatible materials: oxidizers.

2. Polysorbate emulsifiers

Generic name: Polyoxyethylene sorbitan monolaurate, polyethylene glycol sorbitan Monolaurate, polysorbate 20.

Functional Category: Dispersing agent, emulsifying agent, nonionic surfactant, solubilizing agent, suspending agent, wetting agent.

Appearance: Viscous liquid

Refractive index: 1.4685

HLB value: 16.7

CMC value: 60mg/l

Flash point: 110°C- closedcup

Structure of Tween 20

1. Tween 80

BP: Polysorbate80 **JP:** Polysorbate80

PhEur: Polysorbate80

USP-NF: Polysorbate80

Synonym: CapmulPOE-O; CremophorPS80; Crillet4; polyoxyethylene20oleate: polysorbatum 80 and Tween 80.

Empirical Formula: C₆₄H₁₂₄O₂₆

Odor: Characteristic odor

Taste: Bitter taste

HLB value	Acidvalue (%)	Hydroxyl Value	Moisture Content	Specific Gravityat25° C	Viscosity (mPs)
15.0	2.0	65-80	3.0	1.08	425

Typical properties of Tween 80

2. PEG400

Generic name: Macrogols, Polyethylene glycol

Chemical name: α-Hydro-ω-hydroxypropyl(oxy-1,2-ethanediyl)

Empirical formula: HOCH₂(CH₂OCH₂)_mCH₂OH where represents the average number of oxyethylene groups. (m=8.7)

Average Molecular weight: 380-420

Chemical formula: H(OCH₂CH₂)_nOH

Functional category: Ointment base; plasticizer; solvent; suppository base; tablet and capsule lubricant

Physicochemical property

Physical state: Liquid

Colour: Clear

Odour: Odourless

Specific gravity: 1.1254(water=1)

Density: 1.11–1.14g/cm³ at25°C

Flash point: 238°C

Freezing point: 4-8°C

pH of 5% solution:4.0-7.0

Viscosity(dynamic): 105-130cPand7.4cStat99°C

Refractive index: 1.465

Stability and Reactivity: Stable under ordinary conditions of use and storage.

Hazardous Polymerization: not occur.

Incompatibilities: Incompatible with polymerization catalysts (peroxides, persulfates) and accelerators, strong oxidizers, strong bases and strong acids.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Nabumetone

Organoleptic Characterization:

Identification	Observation
Appearance	Crystalline powder.
Colour	Whiteto off-White
Odour	Odourless.

Thermal Analysis:

A. Determination of Melting Point:

The Melting point Nabumetone was determined and it was found to be in range 78- 82°C which complies with standard, indicating purity of drug.

Sr. No	Method	Reported Range	Observed Value
1	Open capillary tube method	78-82°C	82°C

Ultra violet spectroscopy:

Determination of λ_{max} of Nabumetone:

The spectrum of Nabumetone showed λ_{max} at 332 nm it complies with reported value.

Standard Calibration Curve of Nabumetone:

Calibration Curve in Ethanol:

The UV spectrum of Nabumetone was obtained by scanning different concentration of Nabumetone in the range of 2-20 μ g/ml between 200-400 nm using a UV Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800). Absorbance of solution observed on UV spectrophotometer at 332 nm. Absorbance Vs Concentration graph plotted. It followed beers lamberts law.

Absorbance data of Nabumetone for calibration curve in Ethanol

Concentration(μ g/ml)	Absorbance(nm)
2	0.123 \pm 0.0028
4	0.197 \pm 0.0036
6	0.274 \pm 0.0024
8	0.324 \pm 0.0049
10	0.406 \pm 0.0033
12	0.492 \pm 0.0068

n=3, Mean \pm S.D.

The equation is as follows: $Y=mx+c$ Where, Y =absorbance, m =slope, x =concentration.

Calibration Curve of Nabumetone in Methanol

The UV spectrum of Nabumetone was obtained by scanning different concentration of Nabumetone in the range of 2-20 μ g/ml between 200-400 nm using a

UV Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800). Absorbance of solution observed on UV spectrophotometer at 332 nm. Absorbance Vs Concentration graph plotted. It followed beers lamberts law.

Absorbance data of Nabumetone for calibration curve in Methanol

Concentration(μ g/ml)	Absorbance(nm)
2	0.139 \pm 0.0041
4	0.276 \pm 0.0016
6	0.389 \pm 0.0040
8	0.469 \pm 0.0033
10	0.527 \pm 0.0044

Calibration Curve of Nabumetone in Phosphate buffer pH 7.4

The UV spectrum of Nabumetone was obtained by scanning different concentration of Nabumetone in the range of 2-20 μ g/ml between 200-400 nm using a UV Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800).

Absorbance of solution observed on UV spectrophotometer at 332m nm. Absorbance Vs Concentration graph plotted. It followed beers lamberts law.

Absorbance data of Nabumetone for calibration curve in phosphate buffer pH 7.4

Concentration(μ g/ml)	Absorbance(nm)
2	0.183 \pm 0.002
4	0.266 \pm 0.006
6	0.324 \pm 0.002
8	0.476 \pm 0.005
10	0.547 \pm 0.003
12	0.618 \pm 0.008

$n=3$, Mean \pm S.D.

The equation is as follows: $Y=mx+c$ Where, Y =absorbance, m =slope, x =concentration.

Standard Calibration Curve of Nabumetone in phosphate buffer pH 7.4

Parameters	Result
Mediumfor Calibration Curve	Phosphate buffer pH 7.4
Wavelength (nm)	332nm
Equation	$y=0.9971x+0.0457$
Correlation coefficient(R2)	0.9788
Regression Equation	$y=0.9971x$

Selection of excipients used for microemulsion and SMEDDS

Drug solubility determination in oils, surfactants & co-surfactants

The components used in the system should have high solubilization capacity for the drug, ensuring the solubilizationofthe drug inthe resultant dispersion. The higher solubility ofthe drug in the oil phase is important for the microemulsion and SMEDDS to maintain the drugin solubilized form. In present study,

oils namely capmul MCM, capmul MCM C8, capmul MCM C10, captex 200P, captex 355, castor oil, isopropyl myristate and olive oil were screened for solubilization of drug.

Microemulsion dosage forms for oral or parenteral use based on nonionic surfactants are likely to offer in vivo stability. Transient negative interfacial tension and fluid interfacial film is rarely achieved by the use of single surfactant, usually necessitating the addition of a co-surfactant. The presence of co-surfactant decreases the bending stress of interface and allows the interfacial film sufficient flexibility to take up different curvatures required to form microemulsion over a wide range of composition. Thus, the co-surfactants namely PEG

400, propylene glycol and Transcutol P were screened for the study that again are nonionic surfactants.

Nabumetone:

The solubility of Nabumetone in different oils, surfactants, co-surfactants and water was determined (Table 8.8 and Figure 8.9). The solubility of Nabumetone was found to be highest in Capmul MCM (90 ± 1.25 mg/ml) as compared to other oils while in water it was 0.0191 mg/ml [10]. This may be attributed to the polarity of the poorly water soluble drug that favors their solubilization in small/medium molecular volume oils such as medium chain triglycerides or mono- or diglycerides.

Solubility of Nabumetone in excipients

Ingredients	Solubility (mg/ml)
Oils	
Capmul MCM	90 ± 1.25
Capmul MCM C8	80 ± 1.17
Capmul MCM C10	30 ± 2.57
Captex 200P	32.25 ± 3.09
Captex 355	3.89 ± 2.36
Castor oil	8.50 ± 4.24
Olive oil	3.87 ± 2.40
Isopropyl myristate	2.78 ± 1.44
Surfactants	
Tween 20	120 ± 2.52
Tween 80	100 ± 2.47
Labrasol	15 ± 1.25
Plurololeique	10 ± 3.30
Co-surfactants	
PEG 400	120 ± 3.44
Propylene glycol	Insoluble

The studies have revealed that mixed mono and diglyceride like Capmul gave microemulsion (clear or translucent liquid) and emulsion phases, whereas di- and triglycerides exhibited an additional gel phase. Among individual mono-, di- and triglycerides, the oil-in-water microemulsion region was found to be the largest for the diglyceride. Dispersion of drug in aqueous media from mixtures of mono- and diglyceride or mono- and triglyceride was superior to individual lipids [12]. Mono- diglyceride medium chain esters like Capmul MCM are particularly recommended for the dissolution of difficult compounds [13]. Hence Capmul MCM was selected

as the oil phase. The solubility of Nabumetone was also very high in Tween 20 and PEG 400. Hence these components were selected as surfactant and co-surfactant for microemulsion system preparation.

Solubility of Nabumetone in Co-Surfactant

From above data, highest solubility of Nabumetone was found in capmul MCM as oil. Due to suitability of Capmul MCM as an oil phase as per previous discussion, it was selected as oil phase. All three surfactants i.e. Tween 80, Peceol and Labrasol show comparable solubility of Nabumetone. Thus all of them were taken for further studies. The solubility of Nabumetone was almost similar in PEG 400 and

Transcutol P. Thus Tween 80, peceol and Labrasol were selected as surfactants and PEG 400 and Transcutol P as co-surfactants for SMEDDS preparation.

Drug-selected surfactants compatibility study:

The drug and surfactant compatibility study was designed to evaluate the effect of Tween 20 on the physical and chemical stability of Nabumetone and effect of Tween 80, Peceol and Labrasol on the physical and chemical stability of Nabumetone. This study was found to be very useful because concentrations of surfactants are usually quite high in microemulsion formulations. As data demonstrated in Table 9.2.2.1 and 9.2.2.2, there were no significant losses of potency (less than 10%) in any of the samples. Nabumetone did not show any signs of incompatibility with surfactant and co-surfactant mixture. The results are as shown in Table 8.10.

Drug-selected surfactant compatibility study for Nabumetone

Surfactant: Co-Surfactant Mixture (1:1)	Precipitation	Crystallization	Phase separation	Color change	% Recovery (1 month at 25°C)
Tween 20: PEG 400	×	×	×	×	99.0

Where, √ -Presence and × -Absence

In case of Nabumetone, Peceol: PEG 400 and Labrasol: PEG 400 combinations showed precipitation during 1 month study. Thus they were eliminated from further studies. The remaining S: CoS combinations passed the Drug-Surfactant compatibility test. These results showed promise for a

SMEDDS formulation which could be the way to proceed further to meet the dose requirement for Nabumetone. The results are as shown in Table 8.11.

Drug-selected surfactants compatibility study for Nabumetone

Surfactant:co-Surfactant Mixture (1:1)	Precipitation	Crystallization	Phase separation	Color change	% Recovery (1 month at 25°C)
Tween 80: PEG 400	×	×	×	×	99.3
Labrasol: Transcutol P	×	×	×	×	97.8
Peceol: PEG 400	√	×	×	×	96.1
Tween 80: Transcutol P	×	×	×	×	99.3

Where, √ -Presence and × -Absence

Effect of Nabumetone loading and pH of dispersion medium on droplet size of Microemulsion

The increase or decrease in the amount of Nabumetone would influence the droplet size of the resultant microemulsions if Nabumetone were participating at interface of microemulsion. The

amount of Nabumetone influenced the globule size of microemulsions obtained. The globule size decreased with the decrease in the Nabumetone loading.

Nabumetone (mg/ml)	Mean droplet size (Zaverageinnm)
20	13.6
40	15.32
80	78.3

Effect of Nabumetone loading on the droplet size of microemulsions

The results confirm that the fixed concentration of Nabumetone in the microemulsion compositions (20mg/ml) was appropriate for optimum droplet size.

The microemulsion showed fairly similar mean globule size within range of 15–22 nm when diluted

Dispersion Medium	Mean droplet size (Zaverageinnm)
Water pH 7	15.3
0.1N HCl pH 1.2	21.7
Phosphate Buffer pH 7.4	20

with various dissolution media differing in pH (7, 1.2 and 7.4). The time required for formation of microemulsions after dilution with various dissolution media was less than 2 minutes. The resulting microemulsions were transparent in appearance and they did not show any signs of phase separation and drug precipitation even after 6 hours.

Mean droplet size of Nabumetone Microemulsion at different pH

In-vitro Drug Release Study

In-vitro dissolution study

In our study we used dialysis bag to study the dissolution of Nabumetone microemulsion F2 and size '0' hard gelatin capsules for Nabumetone SMEDDS V1 A and V1B. The reason behind it is that due to high viscosity of oil blend in SMEDDS, the SMEDDS cannot diffuse directly through dialysis membrane and could not form microemulsion i.e. self-micro emulsification will be affected. SMEDDS will stick to the dialysis bag and circumscribe the inflow of release medium and thereby it will hinder the drug release. Similarly hard gelatin capsule cannot be used for microemulsion as the formulation contains water.

Nabumetone Microemulsion F2: When in-vitro release of Nabumetone was studied for optimized formulation F2 in phosphate buffer pH 7.4. The results are shown in Table 8.23 and Figure 8.26.

In-vitro drug release of optimized Microemulsion formulation F2 in phosphate buffer pH 7.4

Formulation F2 releases more than 85% drug within one hour. The dispersed and dissolved molecules from microemulsion can permeate out of the dialysis bag easily. The possible factors may be affecting drug release are (a) Microemulsions with reduced particle size provides more surface area to release drug from solvents and thereby increases drug release rate (b) oil phase of Microemulsion may act as carrier molecules which itself does not diffuse through the barrier but allow drug molecules to get diffused from membrane of dialysis bag. The later statement was concluded during UV estimation of the drug released.

UV method could not be developed for formulation due to interference of oil at same wavelength that of drug, but this interference was not observed after release of drug across dialysis bag. This proves that oil globules do not diffuse through membrane and only drug diffusion was permitted. (c) Another possible reason for diffusion of drug may be a concentration gradient. The compartment consisting microemulsion has high concentration of drug while opposite compartment having diffusion media was lacking of that. So based on concentration gradient the drug started to diffuse from dialysis bag to media. Although, exact mechanism is not known but it can be confirmed that any of these factors may have effect on bioavailability of drug. This in vitro study finally concludes that approximately 85% of the drug release was achieved in 1 hour from optimized Nabumetone microemulsion F2.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Summary and Conclusion The objective of the present research study was to formulate, formulation evaluation and optimize microemulsion systems for oral delivery of poorly water soluble active pharmaceutical ingredients. Microemulsions are expected to be absorbed through the lymphatic route and hence the first pass hepatic metabolism can be decreased. Moreover, because the drug would be in solubilized form and in a fine state of sub-division, the absorption and bioavailability can be increased significantly. The most popular alternative and commercially viable form of microemulsion is self-micro emulsifying drug delivery system (SMEDDS). This system is able to rapidly self-micro emulsify in GI fluids and forms fine O/W microemulsions under the gentle agitation by GI tract movements. Solid SMEDDS would show higher kinetic and thermodynamic stability profile, better patient compliant, transport and storage as compared to liquid SMEDDS formulation. We have explored design and development of oral microemulsions, SMEDDS and Solid SMEDDS for poorly water soluble drugs. The drugs selected for present investigation were Nabumetone and Nabumetone. Nabumetone was selected for formulation and development of microemulsion and Nabumetone was selected for formulation and development of SMEDDS and Solid SMEDDS. We have employed Capmul MCM/Tween

20/PEG 400 systems to formulate microemulsion system containing poorly water soluble drug Nabumetone. We have employed Capmul MCM/Tween 80/PEG 400 system to formulate Self Microemulsifying drug delivery system containing poorly water soluble drug Nabumetone. The optimized liquid SMEDDS formulation of Nabumetone was converted into free flowing powder by adsorption of liquid onto solid carriers. The solid carriers used include Colloidal silicon dioxide i.e. Aerosil 200 along with either Lactose monohydrate or Microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) i.e. Avicel PH101. The drugs in our work were identified and characterized by FTIR and UV spectroscopy and were found to be pure.

The excipients with higher solubilizing efficiency for drug are selected for formulation development. Solubility of drugs was determined in different oils, surfactants and co surfactants. The highest solubility of Nabumetone was found in Capmul MCM. Hence it was selected as oil phase for both drugs. The solubility of Nabumetone was also very high in Tween 20 (surfactant) and PEG 400 (co-surfactant). Hence these components were selected as surfactant and co-surfactant for microemulsion system preparation of Nabumetone. The solubility of Nabumetone was almost similar in PEG 400 and Transcutol P.

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